

Social Dynamics of Data Interoperability

Cultivating conducive environments for data ecosystems

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Welcome

What is this about?

Who's who, and why are they here

Why do we need a focus on Social dynamics?

Data lives in business units and projects

Data is still hard to discover, access and use

Data lives in complex ecosystem – systems, institutions, people

Data supply chains have a mix of formal and informal arrangements

Complex ecosystems

Ecosystem

Box, Sanderson, and Wilson, "National Soil Data Project - Recommendation for a Farmers' Data Market."
Christensen, Jeff, "Australian Biosciences Research Data Cloud", 2017

Why do we need a focus on Social dynamics?

The Australian Research Data Cloud should broadly align with the European Open Science Cloud and other global initiatives. It should support research data management from creation and discovery, through description and provenance, integration and storage, manipulation and analysis, and preservation.

2016 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap
<http://www.education.gov.au/2016-national-research-infrastructure-roadmap>

CHALLENGES AND GENERAL OBSERVATIONS

- The majority of the challenges to reach a functional EOSC are social rather than technical.
- The major technical challenge is the complexity of the data and analytics procedures across disciplines rather than the size of the data per se.

A clash of cultures?

A 'clash of cultures' emerged as a key challenge⁶ from the stakeholder consultation, as historical developments may have led to a chasm between domain specialists and e-infrastructure specialists. Open Science drives two very different communities and cultures together and we lack connective tissue. In the earlier transition of scientific research from a loosely individual elite and intellectual activity to a mainstream, institute-based activity,

Realising the European Open Science Cloud report
http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/realising_the_european_open_science_cloud_2016.pdf#view=fit&pagemode=none

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) builds the social and technical bridges to enable the open sharing and re-use of data.

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) was launched as a community-driven initiative in 2013 by the European Commission, the United States Government's National Science Foundation and National Institute of Standards and Technology, and the Australian Government's Department of Innovation with the goal of building the social and technical infrastructure to enable open sharing and re-use of data.

Sandpits & Engine rooms, Pioneers & Town Planners

Technology

Sandpits & Engine rooms, Pioneers & Town Planners

Sandpits & Engine rooms, Pioneers & Town Planners

Data Markets

Multidisciplinary Approach

(32) Large platforms lead to interoperable/standard data

Data standards and interoperability is increased when the data is held by, aggregated through or managed by large platforms. The size enables scale, which leads to others adopting same standards as used by the platform or developing things that interoperate with the large platform.

Solutions:

(35) Getting data to the facility (anti-pattern)

Context

Potential data providers are currently not contributing data to the facility.

Problem

We have invested in a data facility to enable our researchers in the related research domain to deposit and share research data. However we know that researchers are still keeping their data to themselves and not shar

Solutions

- Lowering the barriers to ingesting data;
- Grants require or encourage the data generated through grant funded activities
- Incorporate facility as part of the workflow of creating & analysing the data.

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Exam

(02) In the Limelight

Context

In a group (eg: CRC), the publicity around activities is necessary for the growth and sustainability of the group.

Problem

The publicity is necessary for the group, however, if it is not shared amongst the participants in an equitable way, it can leave individuals feeling like they've lost the limelight and lead to dissent amongst the group members.

Solutions

Find ways of sharing the limelight amongst the group members in equitable ways.

Consequences

(34) Attracting (the right) users

Context

The VL that aims to bring together several distinct disciplines but we see that one of the key challenges is in getting the two groups to work together.

Problem

(31) Maturing of the Startup

uccessful grow and hit a tipping point in their existence. This occurs when they no ct provides, and instead people come seeking to make use of what they provide. Jcceed till now fail to provide the same level of value and often impede it. At this s to continue to survive and grow.

Possible organising frameworks for patterns - 2

Institutional patterns

- Governance patterns
 - Decision making patterns
 - Decision rights
 - Decision modalities
 - Eg: Consensus based
 - Authority structure patterns
 - Eg: Committee
- Organisational forms
 - Corporation patterns
- Rules

Economic patterns

- Funding patterns
 - Revenue streams
 - Government funding
 - Project funding
 - User pays
- Generated value distribution

Social patterns

- Collaboration patterns
- participation patterns

Technical patterns

- Data interoperability patterns
- Technical architecture patterns

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What does this look like for you?

In your experience how does the social & institutional dynamics play out when looking at interope

What is your take on the Social & Institutional dynamics?

Can we do better?

What does this mean to you, your organisations, your country?

What topics would benefit from a more discussion, clarity and a systematic approach?

Can we codify the knowledge gained?

Can we define signposts to help guide the social & institutional dynamics in differing contexts?

What are the levers that are there that can be used

What are the most effective ways to use these levers? → Patterns

Firm up the
questions and
rethink the title

Breakout activity

Navigating the Frenemy Landscape

Headline

Its difficult to navigate the various individual and organisational (dis)incentives for collaboration within a competitive environment that hamper eResearch adoption and growth.

Problem

Both researchers and organisation have drivers and constraints on collaboration. Drivers include cost sharing and accessing intellectual capital to address complex problems. Organisational rules, and cross organisational governance and funding, all of which are forms of institutions, both enable and constrain collaboration. At an individual level there is competition between collaborating researchers as well as between the organisations within which they work. This represents different scales of the frenemy problem.

Solution

- When you are with Frenemies, collaborate in the space where you are 'friends', and not where you are 'enemies'. For example:
- focus collaboration in areas where there is less competitive tension between collaborators e.g. biodiversity and climate where there is less (science, reputational, business) competition
- Explore new ways of flowing funding through the system to drive collaboration by 'changing the frenemy equation' through for example a community governed fund that increases incentives for collaboration
- Create 'watering holes' - places where there is a high value for participating, even though you have your enemies participating in there at the same time.

Related pattern – eResearch facilities as 'watering hole' to attract researchers and enable/support collaboration

Draft Charter for IG

Possible Charter for IG

Purpose

The focus of this interest group is to identify opportunities for the development of systematic approaches to address the key social challenges and to build a corpus of knowledge on building and operating interoperable information infrastructure (within the Earth and Ecosystem sciences research).

Draft Charter for IG

Objectives

The main objective of this IG is to:

- Identify organisational, institutional, economic and individual aspects that increase the friction to achieving information interoperability.
- Develop a corpus of knowledge, including models, frameworks and patterns that can be applied by practitioners to develop the desired social dynamics that foster information interoperability.
- Identify and develop case studies of solutions that demonstrate the application of the corpus of knowledge on this topic.

Draft Charter for IG

Outcomes

There are two primary outcomes of this IG:

- Create a community of interest on the Social dynamics of interoperable information infrastructures;
- Create a corpus of knowledge on the topic.

Some initial topics that could lead to Working Groups include,

- Problem and solution patterns in Information Infrastructure;
- Governance & participation models;
- Frameworks for trust;
- Incentives and disincentives for collaboration and participation;

Thank you

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